

Reclamation potential in the built environment: A digitised assessment of contemporary façade systems

Appendices

Appendix A

Materials Inventory (including second application)

Where geographical-specific datasets were used, care was taken to ensure that data was representative of European production. Each material was mapped to its second application based on existing available recycling infrastructure in Europe.

Material	A1 to A2 GWP (0% RC) [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	Service Life (years)	Second Application	C ₃ GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	Mitigated Impact [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference
Aluminium Extrusion	7.98	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (primary raw materials) + European Aluminium Report 2018 (extrusion process)	60	Aluminium Ingot (Secondary)	1.28	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (0% RC) in combination with Hydro Aluminium EPD (82% post-consumer content) NEPD-1841-768-EN	7.30	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method
Aluminium Sheet	7.79	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (primary raw materials & rolling to sheet)	60	Aluminium Ingot (Secondary)	1.28	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (0% RC) in combination with Hydro Aluminium EPD (82% post-consumer content) NEPD-1841-768-EN	7.30	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method
Annealed Glass	1.29	¹	60	Flat Glass (Secondary)	0.62	¹	1.29	¹
Anodised Aluminium Extrusion	8.15	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (primary raw materials) + European Aluminium Report 2018 (extrusion & anodising process)	50	Aluminium Ingot (Secondary)	1.28	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (0% RC) in combination with Hydro Aluminium EPD (82% post-consumer content) NEPD-1841-768-EN	7.30	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method
Anodised Aluminium Sheet	7.96	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (primary raw materials & rolling to sheet) + European Aluminium Report 2018 (anodising process)	50	Aluminium Ingot (Secondary)	1.28	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (0% RC) in combination with Hydro Aluminium EPD (82% post-consumer content) NEPD-1841-768-EN	7.30	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method

¹ Hartwell R, Coult G, Overend M. Mapping the flat glass value-chain: A material flow analysis and energy balance of UK production. Glass Structures & Engineering [Internet]. 2022; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40940-022-00195-9>

Material	A1 to A2 GWP (0% RC) [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	Service Life (years)	Second Application	C3 GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	Mitigated Impact [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference
Argon	1.38	EcoInvent (cryogenic air separation)	60	None	0.00	-	0.00	-
Desiccant	1.62	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	30	None	0.00	-	0.00	-
EPDM	2.38	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	30	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Net emissions of recycling mixed polymer waste from ²	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ²
Glass Wool	1.69	³	50	Glass Wool (Secondary)	1.03	³	1.69	³
Laminated Glass	1.54	³	25	Aggregate	0.00	-	0.01	⁴
Laminated Glass: Annealed Glass	1.54	³	60	Aggregate	0.00	-	0.01	⁴
Laminated Glass: PVB	1.54	³	25	None	0.00	-	0.00	-
Mineral Wool	1.11	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	60	Mineral Wool (Secondary)	0.67	³	1.11	³
Motor System	5.57	EPD: Robus R600 Gear Motor #S-P-01809	15	Aluminium Ingot (Secondary)	0.92	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (0% RC) in combination with Hydro Aluminium EPD (82% post-consumer content) NEPD-1841-768-EN. 72% recycling efficiency of aluminium considered	5.25	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method. 72% recycling efficiency of aluminium considered
Neoprene	2.38	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	25	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ² .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ² .
Polyamide	9.24	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	25	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ² .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ² .

² Eriksson O, Finnveden G. Plastic waste as a fuel - CO₂-neutral or not? Energy Environ Sci. 2009;2(9):907–14.

³ Hartwell R, Coult G, Overend M. Mapping the flat glass value-chain: A material flow analysis and energy balance of UK production. Glass Structures & Engineering [Internet]. 2022; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40940-022-00195-9>

⁴ Hammond PG, Jones C. Inventory of Carbon & Energy (ICE). Mechanical Engineering. 2006;

Material	A1 to A2 GWP (0% RC) [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	Service Life (years)	Second Application	C3 GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	Mitigated Impact [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference
Polyester	4.17	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RoW IPCC 2013 method	20	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ² .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ² .
Polyisobutylene	4.19	Oekobaudat	25	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .
Polystyrene	3.91	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	60	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .
Polysulfide	9.16	Oekobaudat	25	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .
Poly-vinyl butyral	5.13	AGC: Laminated Glass EPD	25	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .
Silicone	7.08	FEICA - Association of the European Adhesive and Sealant Industry EPD	25	Energy Recovery Through Incineration	2.41	Emissions associated with incinerated mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .	2.07	Energy recovered from incinerating mixed polymer waste from ⁵ .
Stainless Steel Extrusion	5.57	World Stainless Study 2005 (How to quantify the environmental profile of stainless steel)	60	Stainless Steel Extrusion (Secondary)	2.37	World Stainless Study 2005 (How to quantify the environmental profile of stainless steel)	5.57	World Stainless Study 2005 (How to quantify the environmental profile of stainless steel)
Steel Sheet	2.67	World Steel LCI Study 2020 Release (primary raw materials) + EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method (sheet rolling)	60	Steel Slab (Secondary)	0.55	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	2.56	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method
Stone Wool	1.11	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method	60	Stone Wool (Secondary)	0.67	⁶	1.11	EcoInvent - Allocation, cut off by classification. LCI RER IPCC 2013 method
Toughened Glass	1.47	⁶	60	Flat Glass (Secondary)	0.62	⁶	1.29	⁶

⁵ Eriksson O, Finnveden G. Plastic waste as a fuel - CO₂-neutral or not? Energy Environ Sci. 2009;2(9):907–14.

⁶ Hartwell R, Coult G, Overend M. Mapping the flat glass value-chain: A material flow analysis and energy balance of UK production. Glass Structures & Engineering [Internet]. 2022; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40940-022-00195-9>

Systems Inventory

System-specific quantities for life-cycle stages A3, A4, A5, C1, C2, C3 and C4, were assembled into the systems inventory.

A3 Fabrication		A4 Transportation		A5 Construction		C1 Building Deconstruction	
GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference
0.1470	Energy input (kWh) from an international facade manufacturer. This figure was converted to kgCO ₂ -eq/unit, based on the Well-to-Wake emission factors for electricity and natural gas in The Netherlands, then divided by the unit mass to give a value per kg of facade unit.	0.0191	The transportation distances (km) were calculated based on the distance from the fabrication site in The Netherlands to the site of use in London, United Kingdom. This included HGV transportation to Rotterdam port (85 km), container ship transportation from Rotterdam-Purfleet (282 km) and HGV transportation from Purfleet-London (31 km). The geographically relevant transportation factors (kgCO ₂ -eq/tonne.km) were then taken for HGV transportation and container ship were taken from ⁷ . The transportation coefficient was then taken as the product of the transportation distance and transportation factor.	0.0493	On-site construction was estimated based on the equivalent energy used for the construction of multi-storey commercial buildings from ⁸ A 1:3.4 ratio of facade (sqm) to gross floor area (m ²) ratio was estimated and used to estimate the equivalent energy associated with the construction of 1 sqm of facade (360 kg/sqm)	0.0083	From ⁹ whom completed a study with reference to a large exhibition hall (15,473 m ² net area) to estimate the environmental impacts of two different end-of-life scenarios: deconstruction vs. demolition. The mechanical resources associated with these scenarios included hydraulic excavators, loaders and hydraulic manlifts for an estimated time period. The total diesel consumption by machines (litres) was scaled using the 1:3.4 ratio of facade (sqm) to gross floor area (m ²) ratio, diesel emission factor (kgCO ₂ -eq/litre) from ¹⁰ and facade weight as 360 kg / sqm.

⁷ HM Government. 2021 Government Greenhouse Gas Conversion Factors for Company Reporting. 2021.

⁸ Gervasio H, Dimova S. Model for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of buildings [Internet]. Joint Research Centre Technical Reports. 2018. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc>

⁹ Quéheille E, Ventura A, Saiyouri N, Taillandier F. A Life Cycle Assessment model of End-of-life scenarios for building deconstruction and waste management. J Clean Prod. 2022;339.

¹⁰ HM Government. 2021 Government Greenhouse Gas Conversion Factors for Company Reporting. 2021.

C1 Building Demolition		C2 Landfill Transport		C3 System Deconstruction		C4 Landfill		C4 Polymer Landfill	
GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference	GWP [CO ₂ e/kg]	Reference
0.0091	From ¹¹ whom completed a study with reference to a large exhibition hall (15,473 m ² net area) to estimate the environmental impacts of two different end-of-life scenarios: deconstruction vs. demolition. The total diesel consumption by machines (inc. hydraulic excavators and loaders and hydraulic manlifts) in litres was scaled using the 1:3.4 ratio of facade (sqm) to gross floor area (m ²) ratio, diesel emission factor (kgCO ₂ -eq/litre) from ¹² and facade weight as 360 kg / sqm.	0.0091	For landfill disposal, a transportation distance of 50 km was estimated and multiplied by the emission factor (kgCO ₂ /tonne.km) for Diesel HGV from ¹² .	0.1470	For this study the coefficient for system deconstruction was taken to be equal to that for system fabrication (A3).	0.0085	The energy consumption and corresponding emissions associated with landfill management (compacting and creating a sealing cover) were taken from ¹³ .	0.271	The CO ₂ emissions associated with landfill disposal (polymer degradation and landfill gas emissions) was evaluated from ¹³ .

Transportation factors & distances

Components are manufactured external from the facade system assembly site. Transportation distances for transporting components from their original manufacturing site (global) to the site of system manufacture (Netherlands) were based on consultations with the systems provider. The distance-weighted transport coefficient *DTF*, is the GHG emissions associated with a specific transport mode (lorry, rail or ship) as sourced from HM Government (2021). The transportation factor used for calculated the GHG emissions associated with transportation is therefore defined by:

$$TF (CO_2e/kg) = DTF (CO_2e/kg.m) \times Transport\ distance(m)$$

Justification of reversibility

Connection type	Removability	Reversible / Irreversible
Screws/bolts	Manual fitting can be removed with tools with limited damage to connecting substrates	Reversible
Adhesives: silicone, epoxy, poly-isobutylene	No established method for rapid removal of adhesively connected parts. Manual separation is likely to cause damage to connecting substrates.	Irreversible
Laminated glass: Glass to PVB interlayer	No established method for interfacial separation of PVB and glass for reuse at scale.	Irreversible

¹¹ Quéheille E, Ventura A, Saiyouri N, Taillandier F. A Life Cycle Assessment model of End-of-life scenarios for building deconstruction and waste management. J Clean Prod. 2022;339.

¹² HM Government. 2021 Government Greenhouse Gas Conversion Factors for Company Reporting. 2021.

¹³ Eriksson O, Finnveden G. Plastic waste as a fuel - CO₂-neutral or not? Energy Environ Sci. 2009;2(9):907–14.

Appendix B

Service life data & parameters

Technical service life data for each material/component was obtained through consultations with façade manufacturers. For individual components a combined lognormal-Weibull probability distribution was fitted with reference to the reference service life of the component $SL_{\text{component}}$ (years). The selected parameters for the lognormal and Weibull distributions for an individual component are listed in the table below:

Component System /	Lognormal distribution parameters		Weibull distribution parameters	
	μ	σ	η	B
Individual component	$1.75 \times \ln(SL_{\text{component}})$	0.20	$200 \times \ln(SL_{\text{component}})$	0.90
Component (in system)	$1.75 \times \ln(SL_{\text{component}})$	0.20	$46500 \times \ln(SL_{\text{component}})$	0.50

The resulting probability of survival curve for an individual component with a reference service life equal to 10 years based on the distribution parameters listed in the above table is shown in the figure below:

Age (years)	Probability of Survival	
	Individual component (SL = 10 years)	IGU system (SL = 25 years)
5	99.5%	98.5%
10	98.9%	97.8%
15	76.7%	97.3%
25	1.8%	96.5%
40	0%	52.9%

At a time (years) equal to the $SL_{\text{component}}$, a 98.9% probability of survival is estimated. A 76.7% probability of survival is estimated at a time interval equal to 1.5 times the $SL_{\text{component}}$, and 1.8% probability of survival at the time interval equal to 2.5 times the $SL_{\text{component}}$.

Lingnell and Spetz (2007) **Error! Bookmark not defined.** conducted a 25-year practical study on approximately 2400 insulated glazing units (IGUs) to measure their likelihood of failure at 15- and 25-years. Failure was defined as fogging of the IGU after a period of time exposed to high humidity and accelerated weathering. It was found that at 15-years, 2.9% of units had failed. This failure rate increased to 3.6% at 25-years. IGUs typically consist of nine components. The reference service lifetimes for each component were identified based on service life data from the materials inventory. The distribution parameters for the lognormal and Weibull distributions were adjusted to fit a cumulative lognormal-Weibull distribution that produced a close fit to the Lingnell and Spetz (2007) study **Error! Bookmark not defined.** The selected distribution parameters listed for “components (in system)” in the table above were used to identify the probability of survival of each component based on their reference service lifetimes and the probability of survival of the IGU sub-system. The resulting probability of survival curve for an IGU is illustrated in the figure above. At 15-years, there is a 97.3% survival probability, and at 25-years the survival probability drops to 96.5%. The selected distribution parameters were therefore selected as the best representation of the likelihood of survival

of an IGU sub-system over time t . The same distribution parameters were applied to evaluate the probability of survival of a system or sub-system with more than one component, where the probability of survival of the individual components are calculated using the parameters for “components (in system)”. The system probability of survival is then evaluated as the product of the probability of survivals of each component. As described by the following equation:

$$P_s(t)_{SYS} = \prod_{i=1}^n P_s(t)$$

Where i , describes the first component in the references system/sub-system and n , is equivalent to the total number of components in the system/sub-system. From this, it is evident that an increase in the number of components in a system or sub-system will lead to a reduced probability of survival of that system at a specific time t .

Appendix C

LCEEI

$$LCEEI = \text{Initial Embodied Carbon}_{SYS} + \text{Recurring Embodied Carbon}_{SYS}$$

$$\text{Initial Embodied Carbon}_{SYS} = \text{Initial}(A1 + A2)_{SYS} + \left(\text{mass}_{SYS} \times (A3_{coeff} + A4_{coeff} + A5_{coeff}) \right)$$

Where mass_{SYS} , is equivalent to the sum of the component masses in the reference system. The environmental impact coefficient associated with the system fabrication ($A3_{coeff}$), transportation to site ($A4_{coeff}$) and on-site construction activities ($A5_{coeff}$) are provided in the systems inventory.

The service life of a system/sub-system (SL_{SYS}) is that of the component with the shortest service life as expressed by the following equation:

$$SL_{SYS} = \min\{a_i, \dots, a_n\}$$

Where i , describes the first component in the reference system/sub-system and n , is equivalent to the total number of components in the system/sub-system.

It is assumed that the components are replaced at the end of their service lifetimes. At a specific time interval or age t (years), the total number of replacements (TNR) of a specific component must be evaluated with reference to any irreversibly connected neighbours:

$$TNR = \frac{t}{SL_{SYS}}$$

Where the sub-system SYS , may consist of one or more components: it is the reference sub-system for the component after disassembly. The replacement factor (RF) for a specific component is evaluated based on the following equation where W denotes a *whole* number.

$$RF_c = \begin{cases} \left\lfloor \frac{t}{SL_{SYS}} \right\rfloor & \text{if } TNR \neq W \\ \left(\frac{t}{SL_{SYS}} \right) & \text{if } TNR = W \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Recurring Embodied Carbon}_{SYS}$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \left(RF_c \times (A1 - A2_{component}) \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(RF_c \times \text{mass}_c \times (A3_{coeff} + A4_{coeff} + A5_{coeff}) \right) + \text{Module } C$$

Where c , refers to component, i , describes the first component in the reference system, and n , is equivalent to the total number of components in the system/sub-system.

Module C is evaluated with reference to the current system installed at time t (years), and the components that are replaced throughout the life-cycle before t . For each replacement, there is an associated environmental impact for module C . Thus, a system replacement factor (SRF), that accounts for all of the replacements of constituent components/sub-systems in the system over a specific time period t , is calculated using the following equation:

$$SRF = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(RF_i \times \frac{\text{mass}_i}{\text{mass}_{SYS}} \right)$$

Where i , represents the first component in the system, and n , the total number of components in the system.

The relevant quantities for evaluating the end-of-life stage (life-cycle stages C1 to C4) will vary depending on the recovery scenario. The total contribution of life-cycle stages C1 to C4 for SYS-REUSE, COMP-REUSE, and RECYC are detailed in order below:

$$ModuleC = Mass_{SYS} \times (1 + SRF(C1Decon_{Building} + C2Transport_{SYS}))$$

$$ModuleC = Mass_{SYS} \times (1 + SRF(C1Decon_{Building} + C2Transport_{SYS} + C3Decon_{SYS}))$$

$$ModuleC = Mass_{SYS} \times (1 + SRF(C1Decon_{Building} + C2Transport_{RecycledMaterial} + C3ReprocessMaterial + (0.1 \times C4Disposal_{Landfill})))$$

The RECYC scenario considers a 10% yield loss of materials at the reprocessing stage, hence why a factor for landfill disposal is included for RECYC scenario.

Mitigated Impact

The mitigated impact of the current system MI_{CURR} in the SYS-REUSE scenario is evaluated as below:

$$MI[CURR]_{SYS-REUSE} = P_s(t)_{SYS} \times Initial\ Embodied\ Impact_{SYS}$$

The mitigated impact of the current system MI_{CURR} in the COMP-REUSE scenario (where system is split into constituent components and sub-systems) is evaluated as below:

$$MI[CURR]_{COMP-REUSE} = \sum_{k=1}^m (P_s(x)_k \times Initial\ Embodied\ Impact_k)$$

Where k , is equal to a component/sub-system of interest, x , represents the current age of a specific component or sub-system and m , represents the total number of components/sub-systems in the complete system. At system age t , the current age x , for each component or sub-system will vary, depending on the minimum service life of the component or sub-system. For each component or sub-system, the current age x , can be calculated through the following equation:

$$AgeFactor \equiv t \pmod{z}$$

$$x = \begin{cases} AgeFactor & \text{if Age Factor} \neq 0 \\ z & \text{if Age Factor} = 0 \end{cases}$$

Where z , is equivalent to the minimum service life of the component or sub-system.